

ANALYSIS OF CORRELATION BETWEEN GDP PER CAPITA AND AVERAGE HEIGHT OF YOUNG ADULTS IN 2019 IN 164 COUNTRIES

A Data Management Plan created using dmponline

Creator: Lea Salome Brugger

Affiliation: Vienna University of Technology

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Project abstract:

The aim of this experiment is to find out whether there is a (strong) correlation between the gross domestic product (GDP) per capita of a country and the average height of its 19-year-old inhabitants. For this purpose, data from two publicly available datasets were used: One dataset concerns the GDP per capita and the other contains data about the mean height of girls and boys of different ages per country. Both datasets consist of data collected over the course of several years; the year of interest for this experiment is 2019. The data entries from the two datasets were matched by comparing the country name given in the respective entry. Only countries are taken into consideration for which both datasets yield complete information - in total, 164 countries were considered in the experiment.

Project name abbreviation:

GDP-HEIGHT

Keywords:

GDP, GDP per capita, height, average height, regression, linear regression, 2019

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DATA COLLECTION

What data will you collect or create?

The data that serve as input for the experiment come from two different datasets ([1] and [2]). Both datasets are publicly available and can be downloaded from the URLs specified in [1] and [2], respectively, in a CSV format which is the format the source code for the experiment uses. The first dataset ([1]) is provided by The World Bank and updated annually. For each of the included countries or regions, respectively, (in total, 264) it contains the GDP per capita in current US dollars, from 1960 to the year of the most recent evaluation (as of now, 2020). The sources of the data included in the dataset are World Bank national accounts data and OECD National Accounts data files. The data regarding the average height ([2]) are published by the NCD Risk Factor Collaboration which summarizes data from 2181 population-based studies in a single dataset. For each of the 200 considered countries, it provides the mean height of both girls and boys for each age group (from 5 to 19 years) as well as the lower and upper 95% uncertainty interval and the standard error from 1985 to 2019.

The size of the CSV files containing data about the GDP per capita (given in [1]) is 115 KB whereas the CSV file for the dataset given in [2] about the average height of children and adolescents per country is about 16 MB large.

As a result of the experiment, a CSV file is created. This CSV file contains the raw data produced by the experiment; for each country, there are two entries in the CSV file: Each entry contains the country code, country name and the GDP per capita, which are obviously the same for both entries. The two entries differ in the columns for the sex and the mean height of 19-year-olds of this sex; there is one entry for males and another for females. Therefore, the created CSV file represents filtered and then merged data from the two input datasets. Additionally, two PNG files are generated which display a linear regression between the GDP per capita and the average height of 19-year-old males or females, respectively.

Saving the output of the experiment in the CSV or PNG format, respectively, which are open formats, ensures the long-term usability of data and interoperability. The created CSV file is 17 KB large while the size of the PNG files is 30 to 35 KB; hence, there is little storage required for the output of the experiment.

[1] The World Bank, *GDP per capita (current US\$)*, Washington, DC: The World Bank, 2021. Accessed on: Apr. 13, 2021. [Online] Available: <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/NY.GDP.PCAP.CD>.

[2] NCD Risk Factor Collaboration, *Height - Evolution of adult height over time*, NCD Risk Factor Collaboration, 2021. Accessed on: Apr. 18, 2021. [Online] Available: <https://ncdrisc.org/data-downloads-height.html> under "Country-specific data for all countries".

How will the data be collected or created?

The naming and structure of the folders and files follows the convention defined by Princeton University ([1]). Versioning is handled by using a public Github repository ([2]) for managing the source code and data for the experiment.

The creation of the output of the experiment is conducted as follows:

First, the two datasets described above are downloaded in the CSV format. The dataset concerning the GDP per capita is downloaded as a ZIP file containing the actual dataset as well as two CSV files containing metadata (their file names start with "Metadata") which can be ignored for this experiment as we are only interested in the concrete data. The ZIP file is extracted. The data about the average height can be downloaded directly in the CSV format. The two CSV files from the two different datasets are renamed to *gdps.csv* and *heights.csv*, respectively, in order to better indicate their scope and content. There is a *data* folder in the repository in order to separate the source code and output from the input data. The renamed CSV files are transferred to this *data* folder since the source code for the experiment expects data provided in *data/gdps.csv* and *data/heights.csv* as input. The first four lines of the CSV file for the GDP per capita information are reserved for a header indicating the data source and the date of the last update. Those four lines are deleted before running the experiment since the library used for data processing (*pandas*) is not able to handle "uneven" CSV files well.

A Python application is responsible for processing the data and producing the desired output. Python is used because it is easy to understand and write (one does not have to need a broad understanding of the concrete syntax) and highly portable (i.e., running the script on different platforms does not require changes in the code). Package requirements are documented in the *requirements.txt* file, including the versions of the packages for which the code is designed, for

the sake of reproducibility. The Python script reads the CSV files and saves the content relevant for the experiment in a suitable data structure. The data are then filtered (since, for example, only data from the year 2019 are to be considered) and merged into a single data frame. This data frame is exported in a CSV format (the CSV file is named *gdp_avgHeight_per_country.csv*). Next, a linear regression is calculated for both sexes (with the GDP per capita being the X-variable and the average height the Y-variable). Lastly, the regressions are plotted and exported as PNG files (named *regression_males.png* and *regression_females.png*, respectively). All output files (i.e., the CSV file and both PNG files) are saved in a separate folder *out*.

In order to only produce useful data, countries where incomplete information is provided by either or both of the datasets, are neglected. This is ensured firstly by filtering out rows in the CSV file for the GDP per capita where no numeric value is given and secondly by the way the datasets are merged; if a country is only included in one of the datasets, but not both, it is not added to the resulting dataset.

[1] Princeton University Library. *Research Data Management at Princeton*, Oct. 21, 2020. Accessed on: Apr. 18, 2021. [Online] Available: <https://libguides.princeton.edu/rdm>.

[2] <https://github.com/bruggerl/gdp-height>

DOCUMENTATION AND METADATA

What documentation and metadata will accompany the data?

Metadata about the produced results will be provided in the format specified in the Dublin Core Metadata Initiative (DCMI) standard ([1]) because DCMI is domain-independent and simple to use and comprehend. There is an XML file specifying the metadata; it is located in the *docs* folder in the source code repository.

In order to guarantee reusability, the source code is documented using the widespread documentation generator *pdoc* ([2]). The documentation is generated in a HTML format which can be displayed in any browser.

Information about how to run the experiment, prerequisites as well as the documentation generation is provided in the *README.md* file in the public source code repository on Github.

[1] <https://www.dublincore.org/>

[2] <https://pdoc3.github.io/pdoc/>

ETHICS AND LEGAL COMPLIANCE

How will you manage any ethical issues?

All in all, no ethical issues arise in this experiment. No personal information is processed and there are no participants involved; hence, there is no consent needed for data preservation or sharing. Furthermore, there are no restrictions with regard to data transfer and storage duration since no sensitive data is being handled.

How will you manage copyright and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) issues?

The owners of the data provided in the two datasets are The World Bank and the NCD Risk Factor Collaboration, respectively. Both organizations publish their data under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license (CC-BY 4.0) which allows anyone to copy, modify and distribute the data in any format for any purpose, with the only "restriction" to give credit and indicate any modifications.

The data produced in the course of the experiment is owned by the project members. Access to all produced data as well as the source code is managed by the project members. The produced data will be licensed under the CC-BY 4.0 license (like the utilized input datasets) described above. The source code will be publicly available under the MIT license.

STORAGE AND BACKUP

How will the data be stored and backed up during the research?

Since the storage required for the whole project is only roughly 22 MB, no additional services need to be used.

All project contributors are required to use Git for keeping track of and backing up the data and source code. The input and output data (and the source code for the experiment) are stored locally on the computer of the project creator as well as an external hard disk belonging to the project creator and uploaded to the Github repository ([1]). It is the responsibility of the project creator to manage the backups on the local computer and external hard disk. In case of an incident causing the data to be lost on the computer, the hard disk or the repository, they can be recovered by transferring them from one of the other locations to the affected location.

[1] <https://github.com/bruggerl/gdp-height>

How will you manage access and security?

Since the experiment does not handle sensitive or personal data, no particular security mechanisms need to be in place. Read access to the data is given to anyone as the data and source code are publicly available on Github. Write access to the data is controlled via Github and password protection on the local devices of the project creator, respectively. In order to mitigate the risk that a password (the password for Github or for one of the devices) is cracked, strong passwords that adhere to the most recent recommendations published by the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) of the United States ([1]) are used.

These measurements are in line with the data protection policy at Vienna University of Technology ([2]). This policy is in place as the experiment is created and conducted in the scope of the university course at the respective university.

[1] <https://pages.nist.gov/800-63-3/sp800-63b.html>

[2]

<https://www.tuwien.at/index.php?eID=dms&s=4&path=Data%20Protection%20Guidelines/Data%20Protection%20Policy.pdf>

SELECTION AND PRESERVATION

Which data are of long-term value and should be retained, shared, and/or preserved?

The data are produced in the scope of a university course project; hence, the potential uses in research are limited. Nevertheless, as all used data are licensed under the CC-BY 4.0 license described above and no personal data is processed, there is no reason to destroy the produced data either. Therefore, all data as well as the source code for the experiment are preserved in order to enable long-term reusability.

What is the long-term preservation plan for the dataset?

All data are deposited in a public Github repository named *gdp-height* hosted by the project creator with the username *bruggerl* ([1]). Github is free, easy to use and available to anyone and thus, ensures the accessibility as well as findability of the data. Upon (substantially) modifying either the source code or the data in Github repository, a new version is created, indicated with a new Github tag and release. By establishing this versioning mechanism, it is guaranteed that all different versions of the data are preserved, allowing for better reproducibility.

Apart from the Github repository, the data will also be preserved on Zenodo for the sake of accessibility and findability.

With regard to research data management policies, the policy of Vienna University of Technology ([2]) is in place. The established data preservation plan adheres to the policy.

[1] <https://github.com/bruggerl/gdp-height>

[2]

<https://www.tuwien.at/index.php?eID=dms&s=4&path=Directives%20and%20Regulations%20of%20the%20Rectorate/Policy%20for%20Research%20Data%20Management.pdf>

DATA SHARING

How will you share the data?

The data are made available to everyone unconditionally on a public Github repository and will be available starting from 19.04.2021 under the CC-BY 4.0 license. The naming of the repository (*gdp-height*) indicates the content of the experiment so that users who are interested in the topic (or this specific correlation which is investigated, respectively) can find it easily. Anyone who is interested in the data may reuse them. As described above, reusability is facilitated by using standardized and portable formats.

Furthermore, several persistent identifiers (DOIs) will be created for the experiment using Zenodo: one for the source code, one for the produced data, one for the data management plan (DMP) and one for the corresponding machine-actionable data management plan (maDMP).

Are any restrictions on data sharing required?

The project members do not need exclusive use of the data as no confidential or sensitive data is handled that would introduce obstacles such as, for example, lack of consent agreements. Moreover, since all produced data are published under the CC-BY 4.0 license, no data sharing agreement is required. As indicated above, there are no restrictions on data sharing.

RESPONSIBILITIES AND RESOURCES

Who will be responsible for data management?

The project creator, Lea Salome Brugger, is responsible for managing the research data, implementing and updating the DMP, ensuring that it is reviewed and revised and that all data are backed up, documented and accessible, and ensuring compliance with all related policies. These responsibilities comply with the research data management policy at Vienna University of Technology ([1]).

[1]

<https://www.tuwien.at/index.php?eID=dms&s=4&path=Directives%20and%20Regulations%20of%20the%20Rectorate/Policy%20for%20Research%20Data%20Management.pdf>

What resources will you require to deliver your plan?

There is no training or specific hardware required for conducting the experiment as there is extensive documentation about the source code in the code repository (as described above) and running the experiment does not take up an unusually high amount of resources. All software requirements are described in the *requirements.txt* and *README.md* file, respectively, in the source code repository. No software is needed that is not publicly available for free. Furthermore, there are no charges applied by the data repository.